

DOCUMENT PREPARATION MECHANISMS FOR THE PROFESSIONAL PEDAGOGICAL ACTIVITY OF FUTURE TEACHERS AS FACILITATORS

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Abstract. *This article describes the mechanisms, methods and instructions for preparing documents related to the professional pedagogical activities of future educators as facilitators.*

Keywords: *future educator, facilitator, practice process, professional, pedagogical, activity, preparation, mechanism, methods and instructions, personnel training, document, higher education institutions.*

In Appendix 1 of the Resolution of the Ministry of Preschool Education of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. 30 of 2019 No. 155, number 05 in the list of working documents of pedagogues of state preschool education organizations, the teacher of the preschool education organization of the general type has the following documents including:

05-01 State requirements, educational programs, methodological manual and recommendations

05-02 Educator's personal work plan (Work log)

05-03 Children's attendance book (table, filter, information about patronage and parents)

05-04 Development maps of children

05-05 Work plan of mutual cooperation with teachers is given.

05-01 of the Ministry of Preschool Education of the Republic of Uzbekistan on June 18, 2018. registered in July 2018 with number 3032) "State requirements for the development of children of primary and preschool age of the Republic of Uzbekistan" and the 4th order of the Ministry of Preschool Education of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated July 7, 2018 "The First Step" is the main document of the State Curriculum approved by the decision of the meeting of the Board of Directors.

The manual "Thematic planning of the educational process in preschool education organizations" developed by the Ministry of Preschool Education of the Republic of Uzbekistan must be provided in accordance with the age of the working group of each future educator.

05-02 Personal work plan of the future educator (Work journal) Recommendations are placed on the page after the title page of the journal, and the educator can use these recommendations during his career. On the next page, the main tasks of the educator in the current academic year will be highlighted. The main tasks are taken based on the current tasks of the organization. In it, the educational activities aimed at enriching the activities of the centers, modern equipment, planned activities, cooperation with parents and pedagogues will be highlighted.

The agenda is determined depending on the age of the group and the working hours of the kindergarten. 2 morning physical education complexes should be planned for a month, and attention should be paid to performing exercises without objects from 1-15, and morning physical education exercises with objects from 16-31. It is advisable to write down the morning physical training exercises in a separate notebook or to prepare cards in advance.

The next pages for the future teacher will reflect the educational activity of the teacher, the theme of the week and the period will be shown. In the morning circle, the order number of the reception, conversation, games, morning physical education complex with children is entered.

In the case of changes to the activities in the centers, the name and subject of the center and the equipment needed for it will be written. This space will remain empty if the activities in the centers have not changed.

Working in a general group is a frontal training, which includes training in speech, mathematics, literacy, Russian and Uzbek languages, English, physical education and music. The time of these frontal trainings is determined by the future teacher in agreement with the specialists and approved by the management.

Frontal training can be fully disclosed to future educators, and frontal training can be explained as a thesis to experienced educators. The notebook of the frontal exercise is approved and controlled by the management.

The future educator is told that the travel section of the work journal consists of 5 parts. In these parts, the educator first of all illuminates the observed object, plans the type of work suitable for the object, active games, optional games. While engaging children in voluntary play, the future teacher works with children who need to strengthen their basic motor skills and in them jump, run, climb, throw, roll, walk in different ways and other movements. strengthens

The second part of the day in the future teacher's magazine is divided into parts of individual work with children, fiction, games and activities, in which the teacher will work individually with the child, read, dramatize, tell a story. names of works to be given, memorized, plot-ruled, educational, tabletop, developmental games, birthdays, meetings, puppet theaters, clubs and other educational and educational activities are planned.

And during the evening walk, the future teacher plans observation, voluntary games, conversation with parents. A section on changes in the organization of children's activities is included in the journal, in which the educator will write down information about any changes in activities during the day. For example: The planned excursion was not carried out because it was a cold day. The work journal has a section "End of the week", which consists of 4 parts:

- "What did children know before?" - In this question, the future educator writes how much understanding the children have about the topics given during the week;

- "What did the children know?" - To the question, the future teacher writes the news he received during the week from the children during the work processes in the centers and general groups;

- "What do children want to know?" - To this question, the future educator includes topics arising from the questions and interests of children;

- In "Ideas for the next week", the future educator writes activities based on children's interests and wishes.

At the end of the weekly work plan in the work journal, recommendations and instructions of the management of the preschool educational organization (leader, methodist) are given regarding the state in which the plan is written. This is a methodical help to the educator in making a work plan for the next week.

The work journal must be approved, signed, stitched, and sealed by the head of the preschool educational organization.

This work journal of the future educator of the preschool education organization was

developed for the educators working in the organization. The purpose of this document is to design individual work with children in the morning hours, outings, and in the afternoon based on the state requirements for the development of primary and preschool children of the Republic of Uzbekistan and the requirements of the "First step" state curriculum.

The planning of the pedagogical activity of the future educator in preschool educational organizations is considered the basis of the correct organization of children's life, in which educators define educational tasks, forms of work carried out together with children, and changes that should be made to the developmental environment. will give.

Planning makes it possible to implement an individual approach in the educational process, to regulate information and physical tasks for children.

It allows you to analyze the full implementation of the work plan, monitor the pace of the child's development and create more favorable conditions for them.

This work journal of the educator of the preschool education organization was developed for the educators working in the organization. The purpose of this document is based on the fulfillment of the state requirements for the development of primary and preschool children of the Republic of Uzbekistan and the requirements of the state curriculum "The first step" morning hours, walks, planning to work individually with children in the afternoon.

Pedagogical activity planning in pre-school educational organizations is considered the basis of proper organization of children's life, in which educators define educational tasks, forms of work carried out together with children, and changes that should be made to the developmental environment.

Planning makes it possible to implement an individual approach in the educational process, to regulate information and physical tasks for children.

It allows you to analyze the full implementation of the work plan, monitor the pace of the child's development and create more favorable conditions for them.

05-03 Register of children's attendance (table, filter, patronage and information about parents) The register, filter and patronage book maintained by the educator are interdependent, they are used to record children's attendance are documents that control traffic. Information about parents is also recorded in the notebook. The notebooks can be one in total or 4 notebooks can be kept separately. The order of keeping the books is as follows:

Children's attendance book Children's transportation in age groups is determined no later than 9:00 a.m. every day, and the total number of children arriving is excluded. At the end of the month, the total number of days of arrival and absence of children from the list is published and the results are summarized. In the analysis, the number of children on the list, the exact number of children who came during this month and those who did not come at all are written. Based on this analysis, the children's day is determined. The total children's day and the number of days of child absence with and without reason are written. The surname and signature of the educator who analyzed, and the nurse, confirming the accuracy of the number of children, are signed. The head of the organization checks the attendance and analysis conducted during the month, signs and seals it.

The table notebook must be stitched, paged, sealed, and signed by the leader

Filter book: During the reception of the children, the educator briefly talks with the parents of each child about the child's health, conducts primary medical control. Body temperature, skin cleanliness, head cleanliness (check for pediculosis) and the results of a questionnaire from parents

are recorded in the filter book. The child's screening is conducted in front of the parents.

If the child does not come for three days, the medical staff of the organization will check the filter and the parents will be required to submit a special form of medical certificate issued by the relevant regional treatment organization confirming the reason for the child's absence from the institution. The filter notebook must be stitched, paged, sealed and signed by the manager.

Patronage book: in each age group, it is conducted by the educator on a monthly basis. On the third day of the child's absence, the tutor visits the family (or by phone) and determines the reason for the child's absence. If the child does not come for a long time, the second patronage should be held on the seventh day and the third patronage on the fourteenth day, and the date of each day of patronage and the reason for absence should be recorded. On the day of the child's absence from the organization for three days or more, on the day of his arrival at the organization, the medical officer (doctor or nurse) of the preschool educational organization will check and sign the admission and patronage book based on the medical certificate for the days of absence. If the child does not come to the organization in the next month, the educator will register this child in the patronage book again according to the established procedure. The patronage book must be stitched, paged, sealed and signed by the leader.

Parent Information Booklet: the child's last name, first name, surname, date of birth, home address, phone number, parents' last name, first name, father's name, their place of work are entered in this notebook, and when additional information is received, it is recorded in the notebook will go The notebook of information about parents must be stitched, paged, sealed and signed by the head.

05-04. Development maps of children To complete the development map of children in the group, three cycles of observation are conducted: initial (at the beginning of the school year), intermediate and final.

The initial observation is carried out at the beginning of the academic year (around September). At this stage, each child's initial capabilities are determined, and his/her achievements up to this period are determined. The teacher also pays attention to the existing problems of mastering educational areas, determines what qualities of the child require support, what tasks are relevant for each child. Then, taking into account the child's age at the same time, a map of his achievements in the areas of development is filled out. Intermediate monitoring is conducted at the end of the first semester (December, January). The purpose of conducting this monitoring is to determine the correctness of the method chosen for the child, to determine the dynamics of development. According to the results of this observation, the educator can make corrections to the pedagogic process in cooperation with other specialists when necessary.

At the end of the academic year (in May), the educator conducts a final observation. Based on this observation, it is evaluated how the tasks set at the beginning of the year were solved, taking into account the new results expected in the child's development, the goals for the next pedagogical process are determined. Below we cite the example of the field of development of physical development and the formation of a healthy lifestyle:

Sensorimotorics

	Age		
	4-year	5-year	X 3 n

	3,3 years old	3,6 years old	3,9 years old	4 years old	4,3 years old	4,6 years old	4,9 years old	5 years old	
Kagga rolls balls into the distance with both hands while sitting and standing									
He alternately hits the ball with his right and left hand									
Differentiates different structures and surfaces									

05-05. Working plan for mutual cooperation with teachers In it, the cooperation plan is carried out among specialists and aimed at complementing each other. That is, various recommendations for pedagogues, parents, children and employees working in the future educational organization, prevention of unpleasant situations that may be encountered during their activities, skill schools, training sessions, and creation of comfortable working conditions. a one-year plan will be drawn up. Below is an example:

Implementation of this plan should be carried out in collaboration with experts.

No	Theme	Deadline	Form	Information about completion
1	New year party	27.12.22	practice	In written form

In order for the future educator to become a mature specialist as a facilitator, the main emphasis should be placed on the ability to apply professional documents to the process. By mobilizing their knowledge and skills, high results are achieved by studying and forming documents of professional pedagogical activity.

The most important conditions of effectiveness are the formation and development of general pedagogical knowledge, skills and qualifications, as well as the ability to maintain professional documents. In this, the connection of the experience of professional documents with the study of theoretical courses, the combination of practical and research activities of students during the practice period, the implementation of an individual approach to students, the combination of pedagogical management and self-management occupy an important place.

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